

SECTION OF CHEMICAL SCIENCES

POROUS CERAMIC MATERIAL BASED ON SOLID WASTE OF VARIOUS INDUSTRIES

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Abstract

The paper considers the issue of the possibility of obtaining a porous lightweight material using industrial waste from various industries. The physicochemical properties have been investigated and the mineralogical compositions of the used wastes have been determined. Raw compositions with different waste content were prepared to obtain a porous lightweight material, and their melting temperature and swelling properties were studied.

Keywords: building material, agloporite, industrial waste, flotation, chemical composition, mineralogical composition.

Introduction. Porous ceramic materials are mainly obtained using fusible natural clay materials with the addition of various pore formers. The issue of using industrial waste instead of natural components is always relevant [1-3].

In nature, all deposits of solid minerals are complex. Therefore, an approach is important, in which, along with the extraction of the main and associated components, including the industrial use of various wastes of the main and associated production. This helps to reduce environmental pollution.

Therefore, preliminary studies were carried out on the possibility of replacing valuable natural raw materials - highly plastic clays, which are in demand in the production of ceramic and porcelain products for various purposes, with local industrial waste: aluminosilicate flotation waste copper and fluorite concentrating plants, gray kaolin formed during the extraction of coal from the Angren deposit and as intensifiers of gas formation processes during charge expansion, inorganic waste from the chemical industry - solid waste from soda production and waste from fertilizer production - phosphogypsum

One of the building materials obtained exclusively with the use of waste as raw materials is agloporite, an artificial porous ceramic material obtained by sintering sand-clay materials on a grate in a sintering machine. Porization of raw materials during the production of porous silicate filler is achieved by removing water, burning out organic inclusions and other combustible substances, it should be emphasized that the use of raw materials characterized by intense swelling leads to the

closure of air leakage channels. The melt formed at high temperatures dissolves quartz particles at depths of 10-20 mm, and carbonate inclusions up to 5 mm [4-12]

Based on the analysis of the available literature data, it was found that lightweight porous materials obtained on the basis of aluminosilicate materials and intensifiers of melting and swelling of raw materials can be of considerable scientific and practical interest.

In this regard, it is of interest to study the physicochemical characteristics and determine the melting temperature of the used aluminosilicate raw materials of clays and fluff waste in combination with fluff-forming waste.

To perform laboratory research and design of the compositions of raw materials, as aluminosilicate raw materials, unenriched secondary kaolin of the Angren deposit and clay of the Shofirkan deposit, as well as flotation waste (CPP) of the Almalyk MMC and (ZPP) of the Toytepa fluorite concentration plant, ash and slag Angren TPP, as well as chemical production waste phosphogypsum and solid waste from soda production (SWSP) of the following composition (Table 1).

At the same time, it should be noted that the main criterion for choosing these raw materials, on the one hand, was their chemical and mineralogical compositions and geographic proximity to the location, and on the other hand, the use of waste as a flux-forming composition of ceramic masses. Almost all of the listed mineral raw materials and man-made wastes are located in the Tashkent region.

Table 1

Chemical composition of the initial raw materials

Name of raw materials	Oxide content (wt.%)									LOI, wt. %
	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	TiO ₂	Fe ₂ O ₃	CaO	MgO	Na ₂ O	K ₂ O	SO ₃	
Waste CPP	53.20	15.10	0.80	8.41	1.40	5.00	2.70	3.60	5.69	4.10
Angren kaolin	62.26	18.95	0.41	1.87	1.91	0.53	0.12	1.11	0.12	12.72
Ash and slag	58.77	22.60	1.30	7.10	4.30	1.00	1.30	1.20	1.72	0.71
Phosphogypsum	10.43	0.42	-	0.15	28.78	-	0.04	0.04	40.50	19.64
Waste SWSP	1.10	0.40	-	-	48.10	4.20	-	-	3.80	42.40
Bentonite clay	59.24	15.53	0.99	6.09	1.96	1.71	1.49	1.87	0.14	10.86

The results of the chemical analysis of Table 1 show that the content of basic oxides in the composition of the SPP waste, Angren kaolin, bentonite clay and ash and slag are close to natural clay materials.

Phosphogypsum mainly consists of CAO and SO₃ in the form of gypsum dihydrate with an admixture of quartz, the TOSP waste consists mainly of CaCO₃. The phase mineralogical composition was determined by X-

ray phase analysis [13,14], which was performed on a diffractometer XRD - 6100 (Shimadzu, Japan), with vertical $\Theta - 2\Theta$ goniometer. The study of flotation waste by X-ray phase method revealed the presence of the following main crystalline phases, interplanar distances that correspond to: quartz with $d = 0.334$; 0.181 ; 0.154 nm, hydromica with $d = 0.446$; 0.250 ; 0.154 nm (Fig.).

Fig. X-ray flotation waste CPP

It should be noted that the modern technology for the production of porous materials uses the following basic principles of porization : foaming, burning out organic impurities, water evaporation, sintering, swelling of softened masses.

It is known that the sintering and melting temperatures of raw materials and solid materials are affected by material, chemical and mineralogical compositions, structures and their other physical and chemical characteristics. It should be noted that in the development of charge compositions for the production of agloporite , the temperature of the beginning and end of melting is of particular and very important importance .

To conduct a physicochemical study and determine the temperature of sintering, melting and swelling of silicate mixtures, the compositions of masses of various compositions were designed. For this purpose, the

melting temperatures of each initial component separately and of all tested mixture compositions were previously determined with different variations in the sintering and melting components of raw materials and solid materials, the material, chemical and mineralogical compositions, structures and their other physicochemical characteristics are affected. It should be noted that in the development of charge compositions for the production of agloporite , the temperature of the beginning and end of melting is of particular and very important importance .

In this regard, experimental studies were carried out to determine the melting temperature of each component of the raw charge separately and the charge itself in combination with all components. The results of determining the melting point of the starting components are presented in Table 2.

Table 2

Temperatures of the beginning and end of melting of the components used

Name samples	T melting, °C		Temperature interval, °C
	Start	End	
Waste CPP	1250	1280	30
FPP waste	1380	1460	80
Unenriched kaolin	1550	1620	70
Ash and slag	1310	1380	70
Phosphogypsum	1250	1300	50
Waste SWSP	1280	1330	50
Shafirkan bentonite clay	1120	1175	55

The results of establishing the limiting temperatures of the beginning and end of the melting of the components showed that a number of them have temperature-lowering smooth-forming properties. Wastes of chemical production of phosphogypsum and solid waste of soda production, as well as ash and slag to a large extent, have a chemical composition that makes it possible to greatly reduce the melting, sintering and swelling temperatures of the charge in the production of agglomerite. But bentonite clay stands out with its unique physicochemical properties, which has high plasticity during thermal softening, low temperatures of the beginning and end of melting, which, ultimately, to a large extent allows to obtain agglomerite with a minimum bulk density and good strength.

It is known that modern technology for the production of porous materials uses the following basic principles for pore formation: foaming, burnout of organic impurities, water evaporation, sintering and swelling of softened masses.

Obviously, when considering the physicochemical nature of swelling of materials, it is necessary to take into account the effect of these factors from the point of view of their influence on the optimal viscosity of the fired mass and the uniform distribution of gases over the structure of the material. When studying charge swelling, the following complex characteristic processes of gas-forming substances in the developed charge compositions were considered:

In the initial period, when the charge is heated to 160 °C, physically bound water is removed, with rapid heating it delays the premature development of redox reactions and shifting to high temperatures, have a positive effect on the process of pore formation in the fired charge.

Chemically bound water contained in a number of batch components during heating is removed at 300-800 °C, however, part of the most strongly bound constitutional water can be preserved even under conditions of relatively long firing. With rapid firing, the remaining water is removed at the swelling temperature and undoubtedly contributes to the formation of pores.

Calcium carbonate contained in all used wastes dissociates with the release of gaseous CO₂ due to rapid roasting, it shifts to the high temperature region, and contributes to the formation of a gas phase and swelling.

Phosphogypsum (CaSO₃·2H₂O) also dissociates with the release of water and SO₃ gas, which occurs at the agglomerite sintering temperature, and is one of the main swelling agents.

Combustion (oxidation) of carbon, which we use in the form of a burnable additive, coal waste, begins at the ignition temperature of organic substances, but its main mass is oxidized in the temperature range of 850-950 °C, when the clay component of the mass softens and swells.

Thus, gaseous products of CO₂, CO, H₂O are involved in the swelling process, the content of which depends on the composition of the charge. Also, calcium and sodium chlorides, which are part of the solid waste of soda production, have a significant influence on the process of swelling, early sintering and on the softening interval of the charge, within which swelling occurs. Alkaline compounds during the transition to the melt contribute to the formation of a liquid phase up to 50% of the total composition of the mixture.

Table 3

Compositions of the studied raw charges for obtaining porous silicate filler based on CPP flotation waste

Name of compositions	Fleet departure CPP	Angren kaolin	SWSP	Phosphogypsum	Ash and slag TPP	Waste coal mining (+100%)
C1	60	15	15	10	-	6
C2	65	15	-	5	15	8
C3	65	20	5	5	5	10
C4	65	15	8	8	10	8
C5	70	10	10	-	10	8
C6	75	8	5	5	12	6

The characteristic of the melting and swelling temperatures of the fired charge is one of the main criteria for obtaining lightweight porous filler. Determination of the influence of heat treatment temperatures and the composition of the raw charge on the melting and

swelling temperature of the granules was carried out on the basis of experimental raw materials, where the main component is CPP flotation waste, the amount of which in the charge is 50-80%, as well as gray kaolin and ash and slag, which, by the amount of alumina, silica and

other properties are aluminosilicates and smooth formers of phosphogypsum and SWSP.

To determine the melting temperature of the filler, the molded samples were preliminarily dried and then fired in a muffle furnace in the form of molded cones.

Table 3 shows the temperatures of the beginning and end of melting of the experimental batches. When setting up experiments, both the individual effect of the charge components and inorganic additives on the kinetics of melting of raw granules and their complex effect were studied.

Table 4

Temperatures of the beginning and end of melting of samples based on ZPP flotation waste

Name samples	T melting, °C		Temperature interval, °C
	Start	End	
C1	1210	1260	50
C2	1195	1 240	45
C3	1189	1240	50
C4	1155	1220	65
C5	1170	1235	65
C6	1170	1235	65

According to the analysis of the results obtained, the regularities of the influence of the composition of raw materials on the decrease in the temperatures of the beginning and end of melting were revealed, the temperature range changes downward by 20-30 °C with the optimal composition related to the charge Z4.

At the same time, the melting range in batches based on MOF flotation waste is 55-70°C, respectively (Table 5). The addition of MOF-65% flotation waste, 15% kaolin and 10% ash and slag, as well as 5% TOSP and phosphogypsum to the M 4 charge, reduces the melting point to a greater extent than in other samples.

Table 5

Swelling of batches based on CPP flotation waste

No. Blends	Optimal Swelling temperature, °C	Swelling coefficient	Swelling interval, °C
C1	1165	1.29	50
C2	1156	1.34	55
C3	1145	1.37	60
C4	1135	1.46	55
C5	1120	1.44	75
C6	1137	1.45	65

Thus, the dependence of the decrease in the melting temperature and the increase in the interval on the amount of added kaolin clay, ash and inorganic wastes was revealed, when the melting temperature of the samples changes from 1210 to 1155 °C, and the interval increases from 45 to 70 °C.

At the same time, the expansion coefficient in the studied compositions varies from 1.29 to 1.46 and indicates a high swelling of the charge using kaolin, slag, phosphogypsum and SWSP.

The expansion coefficient of the charge with additives was determined as the ratio of the volume of the expanded granule to the volume of the semi-finished

product granule. The volume of each grain of semi-finished expanded clay crushed stone and gravel is determined according to GOST 5978-12 and was calculated by the formula:

$$V = (\pi D^2/4)^h \quad (1)$$

The coefficient of swelling of clay raw materials was determined by the formula:

$$K_{rev} = V_2/V_1 \quad (2)$$

where V_1 is the volume of a granule (grain) of a semi-finished product placed in a kiln for firing, cm^3 ; V_2 - the volume of the expanded granules of expanded clay gravel and expanded clay crushed stone, cm^3 .

Table 6

Influence of exposure time and firing temperature on the degree of conversion of the optimal charge C4

Isothermal exposure, min.	Synthesis temperature, °C			
	1080	1100	1120	1150
5	0.22	0.49	0.76	0.84
10	0.30	0.64	0.96	0.89
15	0.42	0.69	0.96	0.89

The degree of transformation into a porous light weight of the fired mixture is determined by the formula:

$$\alpha = (\gamma_0 - \gamma_i) / \gamma_0 \quad (3)$$

where: α - degree of transformation; γ_0 - density of the initial granules, g/cm^3 ($\gamma_0 = 2.11$); γ_i - density of fired granules, g/cm^3 .

As a result, a direct dependence of the degree of transformation on the temperature and duration of firing was established:

$$\alpha = f(T, t), \quad (4)$$

where: T - firing temperature, °C; t – time, min.

Conclusion. As a result of the calculations using equations, the dependence of the degree of transformation of the charge into a porous material was obtained depending on the temperature and firing time at a given temperature (Table 6).

As a result of mathematical processing of the data, it was found that the maximum value of the degree of conversion of the charge with the optimal addition to 65% - CPP flotation waste, 15% - gray kaolin, 10% ash and slag, phosphogypsum and 8% SWSP is possible with a holding time of 9.5 minutes. and at a firing temperature of 1120°C.

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